

Multi-level determinants of HPV vaccine uptake in Sub-Saharan Africa: Socio-cultural, structural, and systemic perspectives

James Success ODUBIA ^{1,*}, Sunday Ezekiel AJILEYE ², Marvelous Oyeboade OYEDIRAN ², Blessing Okah ADAGBON ², Florence Abosede SAMUEL ² and Damilola Halimot NURENI ²

¹ Department of Health Promotion, Faculty of Public Health, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria.

² Department of Epidemiology and Medical Statistics, Faculty of Public Health, Ibadan University of Ibadan.

³ Department of Environmental Health Sciences, Faculty of Public Health, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria.

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Abstract

Background: Human papillomavirus (HPV) is a leading cause of cervical cancer and related diseases, placing a disproportionate burden on women in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). Despite the availability of highly effective vaccines, uptake across the region remains markedly low.

Research Design: This study is a systematic review examining the socio-cultural, structural, and systemic factors that shape HPV vaccination uptake in SSA.

Methods: Guided by the Population, Exposure, Outcome (PEO) framework and the Socio-Ecological Model, evidence was synthesized from 12 qualitative, quantitative, and mixed-methods studies identified through peer-reviewed databases and grey literature. Thematic analysis was applied to extract determinants influencing vaccine uptake.

Findings: Persistent barriers included misinformation linking vaccination to infertility and side effects, spiritual and cultural concerns, low parental education, weak health infrastructure, and inconsistent vaccine supply. Conversely, uptake was facilitated by strong government leadership, school-based vaccination programs, the involvement of trusted community figures, and transparent public health campaigns. Rwanda emerged as a success case where political commitment and integrated strategies significantly boosted coverage.

Conclusion: HPV vaccine uptake in SSA is mediated by interconnected cultural narratives, health system capacity, and institutional trust. Improving coverage requires multi-level interventions that integrate community-based education, expanded delivery strategies, and sustained political and policy commitment.

Keywords: HPV vaccination barriers; HPV vaccination facilitators; Sub-Saharan Africa; Vaccine acceptance; Public health interventions

1. Introduction

Human papillomavirus (HPV) is one of the most common sexually transmitted infections globally and a major cause of cervical cancer, as well as other malignancies including anal, penile, oropharyngeal cancers, and genital warts (Jensen et al., 2024). Cervical cancer alone ranks as the fourth most common cancer among women worldwide, accounting for nearly 690,000 new cases annually, of which about 90% are attributed to HPV infection (Martel et al., 2020). The burden is particularly acute in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), where HPV prevalence is estimated at 24%, the highest globally,

* Corresponding author: James Success ODUBIA

compared to 14% in Latin America (WHO, 2024). This disproportionate prevalence contributes to high morbidity and mortality in the region, exacerbated by limited access to prevention and screening services.

The introduction of HPV vaccines Cervarix, Gardasil, and Gardasil 9 marks a significant milestone in global cancer prevention. These vaccines are safe, highly immunogenic, and effective against the most oncogenic HPV strains (Bergman et al., 2019). Yet, despite clear evidence of effectiveness, vaccine uptake in SSA remains alarmingly low. WHO (2024) reports that first-dose coverage in the region was just 33% in 2022, far below the 90% global target set under the WHO's cervical cancer elimination strategy for 2030. Several countries in SSA, such as Rwanda, The Gambia, Kenya, Liberia, and more recently Nigeria, have integrated HPV vaccination into their national immunisation programs, often supported by international partnerships and local awareness campaigns (Kanmodi et al., 2023). Rwanda, in particular, is frequently cited as a model of success, where strong government commitment and community engagement achieved impressive coverage rates. Nonetheless, across much of the region, uptake remains limited, leading to rising incidence and mortality from cervical cancer and other HPV-related diseases. Existing studies have largely documented barriers to HPV vaccine uptake in SSA, including misinformation about infertility, fears of side effects, cultural and religious resistance, weak health infrastructure, and vaccine supply challenges (Dzinamarira et al., 2023). While these obstacles are critical, there has been less systematic exploration of the enabling factors such as government policy, school-based vaccination, and trusted community advocacy that promote uptake. Moreover, most available evidence is country-specific, limiting comprehensive regional insights into the interplay between barriers and facilitators. This study therefore seeks to address this gap by synthesising evidence on the multi-level determinants of HPV vaccination uptake in SSA. By examining socio-cultural, structural, and systemic influences, it aims to provide context-sensitive evidence that can inform strategies to expand vaccine coverage and advance progress toward the WHO's 2030 cervical cancer elimination goals.

2. Methodology

2.1. Research Design

This study adopted a systematic review to identify, select, and synthesise evidence on barriers and facilitators of HPV vaccine uptake in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). The approach was appropriate as it consolidates existing evidence rather than relying on anecdotal observations (Moosapour et al., 2021). Given the heterogeneity of health systems and sociocultural contexts in SSA, both qualitative and quantitative studies were included: quantitative research provided statistical generalisations, while qualitative studies offered insights into perceptions, cultural norms, and systemic issues that cannot be quantified. To minimise bias associated with geography or study design, particular attention was given to regional representation and under-researched populations, with critical reflections on patterns of research neglect (Shaheen et al., 2023). The review was conducted in line with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA 2020) guidelines to ensure rigour, transparency, and reproducibility (Page et al., 2021).

2.2. Search Strategy

Boolean operators "AND" and "OR" were applied to refine sensitivity and specificity, using the string: ("*Human papillomavirus vaccines*" OR "*HPV vaccination*") AND ("*Uptake*" OR "*Acceptability*" OR "*Utilisation*") AND ("*Barriers*" OR "*Facilitators*") AND ("*Sub-Saharan Africa*" OR *list of SSA countries*). Searches were conducted in PubMed, MEDLINE, EMBASE, and Google Scholar. To address the under-representation of African research in global databases (Asubiaro, 2023), grey literature sources, including organisational websites (e.g., WHO, Gavi, UNICEF), were also reviewed. Incorporating grey literature helped capture policy documents and programmatic reports that provide critical insights into implementation barriers and facilitators (Paez, 2017).

2.3. Inclusion Criteria

- Studies involving individuals eligible for HPV vaccination in Sub-Saharan Africa (e.g., adolescents, parents/guardians, healthcare workers).
- Research addressing HPV vaccine uptake, perceptions, barriers, or facilitators.
- Studies published in English between 2015 and 2025.
- Qualitative, quantitative, or mixed-methods designs.
- Grey literature such as programmatic reports or policy documents relevant to SSA.

2.4. Exclusion Criteria

- Studies conducted outside Sub-Saharan Africa.
- Research focusing solely on vaccine efficacy, immunogenicity, or biological mechanisms.
- Non-English publications.
- Studies not addressing barriers or facilitators of HPV vaccine uptake.

2.5. Study Selection

The selection of studies followed the PRISMA 2020 guidelines to maintain transparency and methodological rigour (Figure 1). A total of 569 records were initially retrieved: 12 from PubMed, 5 from MEDLINE, none from EMBASE, and 552 from Google Scholar. An additional 6 records were identified through manual searches of grey literature and organisational websites such as WHO, Gavi, and UNICEF. After removing 103 duplicates, 472 unique records remained. These were screened by title and abstract using Rayyan software, which facilitated blinded and structured review, reducing the risk of selection bias. Of these, 430 were excluded for reasons including irrelevance to HPV vaccination in SSA, a sole focus on immunogenicity, or examination of non-eligible populations. Forty-two full-text articles were then reviewed, of which 30 were excluded for not addressing barriers or facilitators, concentrating only on vaccine efficacy, or lacking sufficient data on uptake. Ultimately, 12 studies met all eligibility criteria and were included in the final synthesis.

Figure 1 PRISMA Flowchart

2.6. Data Extraction

Information was retrieved on determinants of HPV vaccine uptake, focusing on cultural perceptions, community attitudes, institutional and policy support, and health system constraints (table 1). Studies spanned several SSA countries, offering diverse regional contexts. Of the twelve studies included, eight were qualitative, three employed mixed methods, and one was quantitative. Populations studied included adolescents, caregivers, educators, and health workers, while policymakers and male stakeholders were less represented. Variation in sample sizes limited cross-study comparability and the extent of generalization.

Table 1 Summary/Data Extracted from the Articles Included in the Review

Authors and Date	Title of Article	Aim of the Study	Type of Study	Study Population	Summary of Study
Balogun and Omotade (2018)	“She must have been sleeping around”...: Contextual interpretations of cervical cancer and views regarding HPV vaccination for adolescents in selected communities in Ibadan, Nigeria.	This study explored contextual interpretations of stakeholders regarding cervical cancer and HPV vaccines for adolescents in five selected communities in Ibadan, Nigeria.	Qualitative	Twenty focus group discussions and four key informant interviews were conducted.	The study discovered widespread misconceptions that link cervical cancer to promiscuity, and found that cultural and moralistic beliefs negatively influenced the acceptance of HPV vaccination.
Balogun and Omotade (2022)	Facilitators and barriers of healthcare workers’ recommendation of HPV vaccine for adolescents in Nigeria: views through the lens of the theoretical domains framework	This study therefore explored the facilitators and barriers for the recommendation of the HPV vaccine for adolescents by HCWs in Ibadan, Nigeria using the Theoretical Domain Framework (TDF).	Qualitative	14 purposively selected HCWs who were in charge of vaccination.	Barriers included a lack of training and an inadequate supply chain; facilitators involved trust in health authorities and professional responsibility.
Hasahya <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Beliefs, perceptions and health-seeking behaviours in relation to cervical cancer: a qualitative study among women in Uganda following completion of an HPV vaccination campaign	This project explored beliefs, attitudes, perceptions, and health-seeking behaviours in relation to cervical cancer among women in Uganda after an HPV vaccination project was rolled out.	Qualitative	Six focus group discussions (FGDs) that included 36 women, aged 25-49 years,	The study identified gaps in knowledge regarding the HPV and cervical cancer post-vaccination campaign, along with persistent fears about vaccine safety and fertility.
Islam <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Acceptability of two- versus three-dose human papillomavirus vaccination schedule among providers and mothers of adolescent girls: a mixed-methods study	To assess acceptability of two- vs. three-dose HPV vaccine schedules among mothers and healthcare providers.	Mixed Methods	Providers and mothers in 5 LMICs (including SSA countries)	Found preference for two-dose schedule due to perceived lower logistical and financial burden; trust in healthcare systems was key to acceptability.
Kamya <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Evaluating Global Health Partnerships: A Case Study of a Gavi	To evaluate Uganda’s experience with the	Qualitative	7 in-depth interviews, 11 network surveys and document review	Highlighted challenges in coordination and application

	HPV Vaccine Application Process in Uganda	Gavi HPV vaccine application process.			processes; need for greater country-level engagement and ownership in global health partnerships.
Kisaakye <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Level and factors associated with uptake of Human papillomavirus infection vaccine among female adolescents in Lira District, Uganda	This study assessed the level and the factors associated with uptake of HPV vaccine by female adolescents in Lira district, Uganda.	mixed methods	460 female adolescents. 20 in-depth interviews	The study revealed a low uptake rate of 17.6%, with factors such as parental consent, school-based delivery, and awareness of vaccine availability playing a significant role.
Lubeya <i>et al.</i> (2023)	"When you get the HPV vaccine, it will prevent cervical cancer; it will act as a shield": adolescent girls' knowledge and perceptions in Zambia	This study aimed to understand adolescent girls' knowledge and perceptions regarding the HPV vaccine and discuss its acceptability and uptake implications.	Qualitative	Interview 30 adolescent girls to reach saturation	Revealed partial knowledge of vaccine benefits; misconceptions were common, but generally positive attitudes when informed; emphasised need for targeted educational interventions.
Masika <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Knowledge on HPV Vaccine and Cervical Cancer Facilitates Vaccine Acceptability among School Teachers in Kitui County, Kenya	This study aims to assess primary school teachers' knowledge and acceptability of the HPV vaccine and to explore facilitators and barriers of an ongoing Gavi Alliance-supported vaccination program in Kitui County, Kenya	Mixed Methods	507 teachers in 37 schools,	Demonstrated that higher knowledge significantly predicted acceptability of the HPV vaccine among educators, highlighting the role of teacher engagement in public health campaigns.
Moucheraud <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Malawian caregivers' experiences with HPV vaccination for preadolescent girls: A qualitative study	This study sought to understand attitudes about, and experiences with, the HPV vaccine among caregivers of eligible girls in Malawi.	Qualitative	40 caregivers (parents or guardians) of preadolescent girls in Malawi	Found mixed feelings; caregivers desired more consistent, transparent information from healthcare workers; mistrust in government and concerns

					about side effects were barriers.
Turiho <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Perceptions of human papillomavirus vaccination of adolescent schoolgirls in western Uganda and their implications for acceptability: a qualitative study	This study explored community member's perceptions about HPV vaccination in Ibanda district and the implications of the perceptions for acceptability of HPV vaccination.	Qualitative	The FGDs of schoolgirls and of parents/guardians were conducted separately using pre-tested and translated FGD guides. The number of participants in FGDs ranged from 8 to 12 per group.	Peer influence, misconceptions, and inadequate parental communication were critical factors affecting vaccination acceptability among adolescent girls.
Venturas and Umeh (2017)	Health professional feedback on HPV vaccination roll-out in a developing country	The study aims to investigate the perspectives of health professionals regarding the HPV vaccination program in Zambia.	Qualitative	15 health professionals working in private, government, and missionary clinics/hospitals.	Reported issues with programme communication, vaccine supply challenges, and the need for stronger stakeholder engagement in future roll-outs.
Watson-Jones <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Access and Attitudes to HPV Vaccination amongst Hard-To-Reach Populations in Kenya	The study aimed to investigate access and attitudes towards the HPV vaccine among hard-to-reach populations.	Qualitative	Focus group discussions (n=14) and semi-structured interviews (n=28) with health workers, parents, youth, and community and religious leaders.	The study identified significant geographical and socioeconomic barriers to access and emphasised tailored outreach strategies to improve uptake among underserved populations.

2.7. Critical Appraisal of Quality

The quality of included studies was assessed using the Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP) checklists, which are applicable across qualitative, quantitative, and mixed-methods designs (CASP, 2024). Appraisal focused on clarity of objectives, methodological relevance, participant recruitment, data collection and analysis, and validity of findings (table 2). No study was excluded based on appraisal outcomes; instead, a weighting approach was applied to ensure weaker studies did not disproportionately influence conclusions. CASP was chosen over alternatives, such as the JBI checklist, for its emphasis on reflexivity and ethical considerations, which are critical in culturally sensitive contexts like HPV vaccination (Long, French and Brooks, 2020). Each study was rated on a 0–2 scale across 10 criteria (Appendix B).

Table 2 Critical Appraisal of the included articles using CASP checklist

Author(s) (Year)	Clear Aims	Appropriate Methodology	Research Design	Recruitment Strategy	Data Collection	Reflexivity	Ethical Considerations	Data Analysis	Findings	Value of Research	Total
Balogun and	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	19

Omotade (2018)											
Balogun and Omotade (2022)	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	19
Hasahya <i>et al.</i> (2016)	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	19
Islam <i>et al.</i> (2018)	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	19
Kamya <i>et al.</i> (2016)	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	19
Kisaakye <i>et al.</i> (2018)	2	2	2	1	2	0	1	2	2	2	16
Lubeya <i>et al.</i> (2023)	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	19
Masika <i>et al.</i> (2015)	2	2	2	2	2	0	1	2	2	2	17
Moucheraud <i>et al.</i> (2023)	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	19
Turiho <i>et al.</i> (2017)	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	19
Venturas and Umeh (2017)	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	19
Watson-Jones <i>et al.</i> (2015)	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	19
Total	24	24	24	23	24	10	22	24	24	24	223

$$QA = \frac{\text{Total Score Obtained}}{\text{Total possible score if each article get the maximum score}} \times 100$$

$$223/240 \times 100 = 92.91\%$$

Applying the quality assessment formula: $QA = (\text{Total Score Obtained} \div \text{Total Maximum Score}) \times 100$ by Odubia, Akinrinade, et al. (2025). The overall quality score across studies was 92.9%, indicating strong methodological rigour. Exemplary alignment of objectives and design was noted in Balogun and Omotade (2018) and Moucheraud et al. (2023), although both, along with Masika et al. (2015) and Kisaakye et al. (2018), lost points due to limited reflexivity. This gap reduces transparency on how researchers' positions may have influenced interpretation, particularly in culturally sensitive areas such as HPV vaccination. Kisaakye et al. (2018) also scored lower (16/20) for unclear recruitment strategies, limiting representation of adolescents. Islam et al. (2018) provided useful mixed-methods insights but underutilised qualitative contributions. Future studies should strengthen reflexive practice, adopt community advisory involvement, and integrate qualitative insights more fully to enhance cultural sensitivity and generalisability. Full details are presented in Appendix A.

2.8. Data Analysis

Thematic content analysis was used to synthesise findings across heterogeneous study designs (Naeem et al., 2023). This approach was chosen because it enables the integration of qualitative and quantitative evidence, capturing both measurable factors and contextual insights relevant to HPV vaccine uptake in SSA (Ayre and McCaffery, 2022). An iterative coding process reduced subjectivity and ensured consistency (Ahmed et al., 2025).

2.9. Ethical Considerations

This review did not require ethical approval since it relied exclusively on secondary data. All included studies were checked to confirm approval by appropriate ethics committees or institutional boards before inclusion. To uphold academic integrity, only publicly accessible sources were used, with full acknowledgement of intellectual contributions. The process followed PRISMA 2020 standards, ensuring accountability and methodological transparency.

3. Results and analysis

What cultural beliefs, social norms, and community perceptions shape acceptance or resistance to HPV vaccination in Sub-Saharan Africa.

Table 3 cultural beliefs, social norms, and community perceptions shape acceptance or resistance to HPV

Subthemes	Authors	Verbatim Quotes
Fear of infertility, death, or harm	Venturas and Umeh (2017)	“They were saying if they give those vaccines to young girls, maybe those young girls they won’t get pregnant in the future, it will prevent them from getting pregnant, so those are beliefs that they have.” [Participant F (L: 16–18)]
	Lubeya et al. (2023)	“Then there some who say you are not supposed to get the vaccine because you will never have children, you will be barren for the rest of your life.” “They get wrong information from the community. Some say you may die after taking the vaccine (...) they are told that they have just come to kill us all because there are a lot of females in our population. A27,”
	Venturas and Umeh (2017)	“They were saying if they give those vaccines to young girls, maybe those young girls they won’t get pregnant in the future, it will prevent them from getting pregnant, so those are beliefs that they have.” [Participant F (L: 16–18)]
	Balogun and Omotade (2018)	FGD, Senior Girls Public school, participant 3 Said “I can’t get vaccinated because most times when you get too much of anything it will have something it will damage in your body” In an FGD with out-of-school adolescents male, participant 3 said “Because that thing kills people... it is better to prevent it with this vaccine than the one you will spend later, if you prevent it now, it will be better”
	Hasahya et al. (2016)	Some women used to have normal periods but after going there for screening, they start experiencing abnormal periods, some get itching, the signs. (FGD2:W5)
Protection, prevention, and long-term health	Moucheraud et al. (2023)	‘I think this vaccine is very important because women are losing their lives because of this dangerous disease of cervical cancer.’ (Woman, 31 years old, daughter who received 1 dose)
	Turiho et al. (2017)	“Our girls are lucky to have this chance... They have peace of mind because they are confident that their future is free of the cervical cancer disease... We are happy about the vaccination because it saves our money that would be spent treating cervical cancer in future” (FGD of parents)

As highlighted in Table 3, one of the most prominent subthemes emerging from the qualitative studies is the widespread fear of infertility, death, or bodily harm linked to HPV vaccination. These fears, often rooted in misinformation and community-based rumours, played a critical role in shaping vaccine hesitancy. Venturas and Umeh (2017) illustrate this concern through a participant's testimony:

"They were saying if they give those vaccines to young girls, maybe those young girls, they will not get pregnant in the future, it will prevent them from getting pregnant, so those are beliefs that they have."

This statement captures broader community suspicions that the vaccine could jeopardize fertility, reflecting cultural anxieties about reproduction and womanhood. In the same vein, Lubeya et al. (2023) reported similar views from participants, such as:

"Then there some who say you are not supposed to get the vaccine because you will never have children, you will be barren for the rest of your life."

Such expressions reinforce the widespread perception that vaccination could cause barrenness. Lubeya et al. (2023) also emphasize that fears surrounding vaccines are fuelled by international distrust, with some groups believing such interventions might be designed to harm women in particular. Echoing this, Balogun and Omotade (2018) and Hasahya et al. (2016) highlight additional concerns that the vaccine may cause physical harm or unusual health problems, including malfunctions of the reproductive system. Taken together, these findings demonstrate that fears of infertility and bodily harm are pervasive, sustained by misinformation, cultural beliefs, and deep-rooted distrust of health communication.

Contrasting with the negative narratives of harm and infertility, another important theme that surfaced was that of protection, prevention, and long-term health as motivating factors for HPV vaccine acceptance (see Table 4.2). This counter-narrative demonstrates that, when individuals are properly informed, they tend to view the vaccine as a protective measure safeguarding girls against future health risks. Moucheraud et al. (2023) capture this perspective through a participant who affirmed:

"I think this vaccine is very important because women are losing their lives because of this dangerous disease of cervical cancer."

This response reflects awareness of the serious threat posed by cervical cancer and highlights a proactive attitude towards prevention standing in direct opposition to the fear-based concerns discussed earlier. Similarly, Turiho et al. (2017) found that some community members regarded vaccination as both emotionally fulfilling and financially beneficial. Participants expressed relief and gratitude for the opportunity to protect girls from cervical cancer, noting that prevention not only preserves health but also reduces future medical expenses.

"Individuals indicated their gratitude that they had the chance to save girls against cancer of the cervix, which is relieving and saves future costs."

Such sentiments portray vaccination as the most sensible option to avoid illness and unnecessary financial strain. However, these positive perspectives were comparatively less frequent across the reviewed studies, suggesting the need for stronger educational interventions to amplify these views and counterbalance the persistence of misinformation.

3.1.1. To evaluate the role of policy frameworks, institutional support systems, and grassroots initiatives in advancing HPV vaccine uptake across the region.

Table 4 The role of policy frameworks, institutional support systems, and grassroots initiatives in advancing HPV

Subthemes	Authors	Verbatim Quotes
Teachers, health workers, and media	Turiho et al. (2017)	"I was well taught by my teachers and the health workers who came to our school that the HPV vaccination would protect me from cervical cancer, which can lead to failure to produce children... With HPV vaccination, we shall have healthy lives in future and be able to give birth to children..." (FGD of schoolgirls)
	Kisaakye et al. (2018)	"The teachers told us that the HPV vaccine is important and protects against cervical cancer but did not explain to us well the intervals and doses" (In-depth interview 7)"
	Moucheraud et al. (2023)	"I heard it on the radio, but I had my own doubts... when my friend explained to me about his relative who was found with the cancer, I started to believe." (Man, 34 years old, daughter who received 2 doses)"
Government and partner involvement	Kamya et al. (2016)	"The MoH took a lead in HPV application process... The government is currently taking the leading role in these processes unlike the past. However, PATH played a critical role. PATH continued reminding MoH of the need to prioritise the HPV [vaccine] introduction" (Development partner). "PATH continued reminding MoH of the need to prioritise the HPV [vaccine] introduction"
	Balogun and Omotade (2022)	'...including it in the NPI...it gives a mother a sense of obligation that I need to vaccinate my child' Family Physician 1, Tertiary HF
Trust in health system and perceived efficacy	Lubeya et al. (2023)	"The vaccine is very important to us, it prevents us from getting the cervical cancer. At some point we can be sexually active but if we never had that vaccine, HPV can be easily transmitted into us cos (sic) it comes as a foreign material. So as for that when you get the (HPV) vaccine it will prevent cervical cancer (hmm), it will act as a shield of course. A22"
	Watson-Jones et al. (2015)	"The Maasai have started understanding the importance [of vaccines]. we have seen they have really helped a lot, becausemany children used to be born with polio but nowa days it is difficult to find children with polio." (Religious Leader, FGD Kajiado) "The vaccine will be accepted since it has come from the government and they know the government cannot come up with something to destroy their children." (Community leader, SSI Korogocho)
	Islam et al. (2018)	"Most providers (75%) reported that they would recommend a 2-dose compared to 3-dose schedule, ranging from 45% in South Africa
Accessibility and visibility	Moucheraud et al. (2023)	"[School-based vaccination] is an advantage because it is administered in public and not privately...People think something wrong is going on when you are doing things in private." (Woman, 37 years, daughter who received 1 dose)
	Watson-Jones et al. (2015)	"For those children that live far, maybe leaving the school and going to a health facility will be hard. If it is in school, just do it there." (Mother, FGD Korogocho).
	Turiho et al. (2017)	"Most of us encouraged our daughters to be vaccinated... We would be willing that our girls get vaccinated in future because no one has seen any adverse side effects of the vaccine" (FGD of parents).

Across the reviewed studies, the influence of teachers, health workers, and media on HPV vaccine uptake in Sub-Saharan Africa stood out as a recurring theme (see Table 4). These actors often served as trusted messengers, bridging the gap between public health programs and communities. Turiho et al. (2017) illustrate this through the positive impact of school-based education, as one participant recalled:

"I was well taught by my teachers and the health workers who came to our school that the HPV vaccination would protect me from cervical cancer, which can lead to failure to produce children... With HPV vaccination, we shall have healthy lives in future and be able to give birth to children..."

This testimony shows how school-based sensitisation effectively framed the vaccine as both a safeguard for fertility and a pathway to future well-being directly challenging prevailing fears of infertility. Yet, the delivery of such messages was not always comprehensive. For instance, Kisaakye et al. (2018) reported that some students felt inadequately informed:

"The teachers told us that the HPV vaccine is important and protects against cervical cancer but did not explain to us well the intervals and doses."

This gap illustrates how insufficient or vague communication can foster confusion and undermine vaccine acceptance. Similarly, while mass media such as radio were sometimes used to raise awareness, Moucheraud et al. (2023) observed that these efforts often fell short. Participants tended to place more confidence in information received from familiar individuals, especially when accompanied by lived experience. Together, these findings emphasise that although teachers, healthcare providers, and the media all play significant roles, their influence is strongest when messages are clear, consistent, and grounded in relatable, community-based experiences.

Another significant enabler of HPV vaccine uptake identified in the studies was the involvement of governments and international partners. These actors offered the policy frameworks, institutional support, and resources needed for vaccine introduction and sustainability. Kanya et al. (2016) illustrate this dynamic with the observation:

"The MoH took a lead in HPV application process... The government is currently taking the leading role in these processes unlike the past. However, PATH played a critical role. PATH continued reminding MoH of the need to prioritise the HPV [vaccine] introduction" (Development partner).

This example underscores how government ownership was central to implementation, while partners such as PATH provided vital advocacy and technical support to ensure progress. Policy integration also emerged as a powerful influence. Balogun and Omotade (2022) reported that incorporating the vaccine into the National Programme on Immunisation (NPI) enhanced parental commitment, as reflected in the words of a family physician:

"...including it in the NPI...it gives a mother a sense of obligation that I need to vaccinate my child" (Family Physician 1, Tertiary HF).

By embedding the HPV vaccine into formal immunisation schedules, governments were able to signal legitimacy, safety, and necessity, thereby reinforcing public trust. Nonetheless, the evidence also suggests that while such leadership and partner engagement were crucial facilitators, continuous follow-up and sustained commitment from these stakeholders remain essential to preserve momentum and maximise vaccine uptake.

Trust in the health system and confidence in the protective power of the HPV vaccine were repeatedly identified as major facilitators of uptake. When individuals could clearly connect the vaccine to disease prevention and long-term health benefits, acceptance was stronger. Lubeya et al. (2023) provide an example of this perspective through a participant's explanation:

"The vaccine is very important to us, it prevents us from getting the cervical cancer. At some point, we can be sexually active but if we never had that vaccine, HPV can be easily transmitted into us coz (sic) it comes as a foreign material. So as for that when you get the (HPV) vaccine it will prevent cervical cancer (hmm), it will act as a shield of course. A22"

This response illustrates how vaccination was perceived as a shield against infection, particularly as young people approached sexual maturity, showing that targeted health messaging had resonated. Broader trust in vaccines was also reinforced by past immunisation successes. Watson-Jones et al. (2015) highlighted this through community reflections:

"The Maasai have started understanding the importance [of vaccines]. we have seen they have really helped a lot, becausemany children used to be born with polio but nowadays it is difficult to find children with polio."

By linking HPV vaccination to well-known victories, such as the reduction of polio, communities were more likely to view new vaccines as both reliable and effective. Confidence was further strengthened by trust in government intentions; as Watson-Jones et al. (2015) observed, many people believed that authorities would not introduce an intervention that could harm children. Practical considerations also played a role. For instance, Islam et al. (2018) reported that healthcare providers in South Africa preferred the two-dose schedule over the three-dose approach, making access easier and more acceptable. Altogether, these findings show that institutional trust combined with a strong belief in the vaccine’s effectiveness and tangible health benefits significantly contributes to the willingness of communities to accept HPV vaccination.

Accessibility and the visibility of HPV vaccination emerged as powerful facilitators of uptake, especially when vaccination programs were delivered through schools or other public spaces. The act of administering vaccines openly was seen as a way to reduce suspicion and strengthen trust. Moucheraud et al. (2023) captured this through community reflections:

“[School-based vaccination] is an advantage because it is administered in public and not privately...People think something wrong is going on when you are doing things in private.”

This observation highlights how visible delivery of vaccines created a sense of legitimacy, reassuring communities that nothing harmful or hidden was taking place. Practical accessibility also played an important role. Watson-Jones et al. (2015) noted participants’ concerns about distance to health facilities, as illustrated in the statement:

“For those children that live far, maybe leaving the school and going to a health facility will be hard. If it is in school, just do it there.”

School-based programs therefore reduced travel challenges for families while positioning schools as convenient and trusted vaccination points. Beyond logistics, the visibility of safe outcomes helped to reinforce parental confidence. As Turiho et al. (2017) observed, parents were reassured by the absence of side effects:

“Most of us encouraged our daughters to be vaccinated... We would be willing that our girls get vaccinated in future because no one has seen any adverse side effects of the vaccine.”

This testimony demonstrates how repeated, visible evidence of safe vaccination shaped positive attitudes and motivated future acceptance. Collectively, these findings suggest that transparent delivery, ease of access, and visible safety outcomes work together to reduce both practical and psychological barriers, ultimately encouraging greater HPV vaccine uptake in Sub-Saharan Africa.

3.1.2. To investigate the multi-layered constraints ranging from individual attitudes to structural and systemic health barriers that hinder HPV vaccination implementation in diverse Sub-Saharan African contexts.

Table 5 The multi-layered constraints ranging from individual attitudes to structural and systemic health barriers that hinder HPV vaccination

Subthemes	Authors	Verbatim Quotes
Infertility, satanism, blood collection	Lubeya et al. (2023)	“Some were saying that oh maybe these people they are just here to get the blood for this what uh witchcraft activities so they want us to donate our blood. There will be that, they will put us into satanism. A22, vaccinated
	Moucheraud et al. (2023)	“Women chat in a group and say that the population of female children in Malawi is high, and they are trying to control the population so that the children should not be able to give birth. So, some of us went to consult to the community health personnel, and we explained our worry that the vaccine’s aim was to control their capability to give birth.” (Woman, 50 years, daughter who received 1 dose)
	Turiho et al. (2017)	“...it weakens their intellect so that they do not study beyond primary seven...”
	Lubeya et al. (2023)	“ Some (adolescents) think it’s good, but their parents don’t. So, there may be a bit of conflict between the two owing to the fact that most of my friend’s parents are not educated and hence don’t understand the importance of the vaccine,

Low parental education, disapproval		unlike us students who come here and understand the advantage of getting the vaccine. So, others think it's good while others don't. A13" "My mum just refused me from getting the vaccine but I really wanted to get the vaccine I heard the effects of this disease (cervical cancer) and really wanted to get the vaccine, but my mum refused. A20,"
	Turiho et al. (2017)	"Some parents refused to send their children to school on the first day of vaccination and they missed the first dose. After realizing that the children who received the first dose had not died, the previously reluctant parents allowed their children to get the second and third doses of the vaccine..." (FGD of parents)"
Spiritual, moral, and religious beliefs	Balogun and Omotade (2022)	'People believe that cancer is a punishment from God...it is a spiritual problem so vaccine can never be a solution' Nurse 1, Primary HC
	Masika et al. (2015)	'We have some religions that don't allow modern medicine, so the government should come in and decide what to do with the parent.'
	Moucheraud et al. (2023)	"Some churches instruct their members to never go to the hospital, and we have people who have never received any vaccine because of their beliefs, so I believe that some will never get the [HPV] vaccine because of that." (Man, 64 years old, unvaccinated daughter)
Supply, cost, and access problems	Balogun and Omotade (2022)	'...availability has been a challenge' Family Physician 1, Tertiary HF
	Kisaakye et al. (2018)	"Vaccines were sent without financial support so we had to divert some primary health care funds to facilitate those health workers who vaccinated in schools and community outreaches" (Key informant interview 2)."
	Venturas and Umeh (2017)	"Because money is hard to come by in the current situation that there is, money is very difficult to come by, and there are only a few in formal employment, a large group they don't have anything to do. So they can't even be willing to spare that pin (ZMK 1) on a vaccine, they would rather spend that on food." [Participant L (L: 48-51)]

As shown in Table 5, misconceptions about infertility, satanism, and blood collection frequently emerged as barriers to HPV vaccine uptake in Sub-Saharan Africa. These beliefs often stem from misinformation and longstanding cultural suspicions surrounding medical practices. Lubeya et al. (2023) captured these fears through the words of one participant:

"Some were saying that oh maybe these people they are just here to get the blood for this what uh witchcraft activities so they want us to donate our blood. There will be that, they will put us into satanism. A22, vaccinated."

This illustrates how vaccination was sometimes equated with witchcraft or satanic practices, particularly in contexts where trust in modern healthcare was already fragile. Concerns about infertility were also prominent, as reflected in Moucheraud et al. (2023):

"Women chat in a group and say that the population of female children in Malawi is high, and they are trying to control the population so that the children should not be able to give birth..."

Such views reflect wider anxieties about population control and international health agendas, often linked to historical injustices and forced sterilisation narratives. In addition, fears about education were also noted. Turiho et al. (2017) reported community claims such as:

"...it weakens their intellect so that they do not study beyond primary seven..."

These examples show how misinformation feeds into irrational associations, yet they do not signal outright rejection of vaccines. Rather, they highlight a lack of accurate information and entrenched community scepticism.

Another recurring challenge was the influence of parental education and disapproval on adolescent vaccine uptake. Limited health literacy among parents often led to conflicts between informed students and less-informed guardians. As Lubeya et al. (2023) reported:

"Some (adolescents) think it's good, but their parents don't. So, there may be a bit of conflict between the two owing to the fact that most of my friend's parents are not educated and hence don't understand the importance of the vaccine, unlike us students who come here and understand the advantage of getting the vaccine. So, others think it's good while others don't. A13."

This shows the tension created when adolescents recognised the value of the vaccine, but parental authority prevented uptake. In some cases, refusal was absolute, as illustrated in another account:

"My mum just refused me from getting the vaccine but I really wanted to get the vaccine I heard the effects of this disease (cervical cancer) and really wanted to get the vaccine, but my mum refused. A20."

Despite these barriers, parental perceptions were not always fixed. Turiho et al. (2017) found that some parents, after initially refusing the first dose, eventually allowed their children to complete vaccination when they observed no side effects in others. This demonstrates how visible evidence of safety can gradually shift parental attitudes, highlighting the need for parent-focused education alongside school-based efforts.

Spiritual, moral, and religious beliefs were also major barriers, particularly in communities where illness is seen as spiritually caused and modern medicine is distrusted. Balogun and Omotade (2022) reported the following perception:

"People believe that cancer is a punishment from God...it is a spiritual problem so vaccine can never be a solution" (Nurse 1, Primary HC).

Here, cervical cancer is viewed as a divine punishment, making biomedical interventions appear irrelevant. Similarly, some religious sects directly oppose modern medicine. Masika et al. (2015) emphasised this challenge, quoting:

"We have some religions that don't allow modern medicine, so the government should come in and decide what to do with the parent."

These examples show how deeply religious interpretations can shape health decisions, often leading to outright vaccine rejection. Moucheraud et al. (2023) also observed that in certain religious communities, vaccination of any kind including HPV was strongly resisted. Although such opposition is deeply entrenched, engaging faith leaders with tailored education that connects health with spiritual values may help bridge the gap and promote vaccine acceptance.

Beyond cultural and religious concerns, structural barriers such as supply, cost, and access significantly hinder HPV vaccine uptake. Weak health systems and limited resources often lead to stockouts or irregular distribution. Balogun and Omotade (2022) noted:

"...availability has been a challenge" (Family Physician 1, Tertiary HF).

Even when vaccines were supplied, operational challenges persisted. Kisaakye et al. (2018) described financial constraints, explaining:

"Vaccines were sent without financial support so we had to divert some primary health care funds to facilitate those health workers who vaccinated in schools and community outreaches" (Key informant interview 2).

This reflects how underfunded outreach efforts undermine program sustainability. Economic hardship at the household level also compounded the issue. Venturas and Umeh (2017) observed that daily survival costs often outweighed preventive health spending, making vaccination a low priority for many families. To overcome these challenges, governments are encouraged to allocate special funds, incorporate HPV vaccines into routine immunisation programs, and strengthen partnerships with international donors. Approaches such as mobile clinics or incentive-based schemes may also reduce inequities in access.

Rumours of adverse physical reactions such as swelling, paralysis, or excessive bleeding were another common barrier, often spread through misinformation. Turiho et al. (2017) captured these fears through the voice of a schoolgirl:

"I first feared taking the injection because I thought my arm would swell and I end up not doing any work or going to school... I thought I would bleed very much after the injection but there was no bleeding... At the first injection, I was worried but for the second one, I was confident and not fearing anything" (FGD of girls).

This illustrates how initial fears could be dispelled once individuals directly experienced the vaccination process and observed no harmful effects. However, rumours remained widespread in some communities. Lubeya et al. (2023) noted that adolescents often feared outcomes such as paralysis or long-term illness, with some even believing the vaccine was part of a larger conspiracy targeting women. These examples demonstrate how misinformation can escalate into destructive conspiracy theories, deepening distrust. Addressing this requires continuous community engagement, open demonstrations of vaccine safety, and transparent communication to rebuild trust and counter false narratives.

4. Discussion

The findings presented in Table 4.2 illustrate a complex and often contradictory perception of HPV vaccination across Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). On one side, misinformation continues to fuel widespread fears around infertility, physical harm, and even death, thereby discouraging uptake (Venturas and Umeh, 2017; Lubeya et al., 2023; Balogun and Omotade, 2018; Hasahya et al., 2016). On the other, there is an increasing awareness of the vaccine's protective potential, particularly among those who are well informed (Moucheraud et al., 2023; Turiho et al., 2017). This tension shows how community discussions often mediate personal decisions. Widespread anxieties over infertility and harm echo earlier reports by Kutz et al. (2023) and Wilson et al. (2023), who argue that longstanding mistrust and low levels of health literacy create space for conspiracy narratives to flourish. However, much of the literature reduces this issue to a simple divide between trust and mistrust, without recognising the ambivalence many people experience acknowledging the vaccine's benefits while simultaneously fearing its risks. Lubeya et al. (2023) highlight how this ambivalence complicates public health responses and points to the need for updated communication strategies. Importantly, the dominance of harm-based narratives, such as those highlighted by Peterson, suggests that messages emphasising prevention have not been sufficiently amplified. As Murewanhema et al. (2024) argue, this is partly because community engagement has often been short-lived, creating space for rumours to take hold. Instead of dismissing misinformation as irrational, researchers and practitioners need to see it as a form of resistance rooted in colonial histories, medical exploitation, and systemic neglect. Addressing this requires more than campaigns; it requires a deliberate rebuilding of trust through meaningful, context-sensitive relationships.

Turning to Table 4.3, the facilitators of vaccine acceptance include trusted interpersonal communication through teachers, healthcare providers, and media (Turiho et al., 2017; Kisaakye et al., 2018; Moucheraud et al., 2023); government leadership and partnerships (Kamya et al., 2016; Balogun and Omotade, 2022); trust in health institutions (Lubeya et al., 2023; Watson-Jones et al., 2015; Islam et al., 2018); and visible, community-based vaccination programmes (Moucheraud et al., 2023; Watson-Jones et al., 2015; Turiho et al., 2017). While these drivers are significant, they are not consistently applied across the region. Education and trusted intermediaries are widely celebrated in the literature (LaMontagne et al., 2017; Agimas et al., 2024), yet our findings suggest that these actors often communicate partial or incomplete information, which generates new uncertainties. Kisaakye et al. (2018) provide evidence of such gaps, but the literature offers little analysis of why communication is inconsistent whether due to lack of resources or the persistence of hierarchical, one-way messaging models. This indicates a need to move beyond traditional "inform-and-comply" strategies toward dialogical, participatory approaches to health education.

School-based vaccination is consistently praised as an effective model (Guillame et al., 2023; Ezezika et al., 2022). However, this framework excludes young people who are out of school, leaving significant groups unreached. The emphasis communities place on visibility and public vaccination challenges assumptions that privacy and individualised medical services are always preferable. Instead, public delivery reflects a strong demand for transparency and collective reassurance. Similarly, although government and partner involvement are widely recognised as vital (Kamya et al., 2016; Asempah and Ikpebe, 2024), our analysis shows that such partnerships are often unsustainable without ongoing oversight. "Ownership" of health programmes, therefore, needs to be redefined not as symbolic leadership but as long-term accountability backed by resource commitments. Prem et al. (2024) emphasise that sustained engagement from multiple actors is crucial for vaccine programmes to succeed, suggesting that interventions must shift from episodic campaigns to more deeply embedded, community-driven health systems.

As shown in Table 4.4, barriers to HPV vaccine uptake extend across sociocultural, religious, and systemic domains. Reported concerns include fears of infertility, satanism, and blood collection (Turiho et al., 2017; Moucheraud et al.,

2023); parental disapproval (Lubeya et al., 2023; Turiho et al., 2017); religious prohibitions (Masika et al., 2015; Moucheraud et al., 2023); misinformation (Turiho et al., 2017; Lubeya et al., 2023); as well as cost and access challenges (Balogun and Omotade, 2022; Kisaakye et al., 2018; Venturas and Umeh, 2017). These challenges cannot be understood in isolation, as they are embedded in wider histories of marginalisation and uneven development. While prior studies often frame spiritual concerns as superstition and supply issues as technical, our analysis highlights their interconnection. For instance, fears of satanism are not merely irrational beliefs but express anxieties over autonomy, sovereignty, and the hidden agendas of global health actors (Wilson et al., 2023; Moucheraud et al., 2023). Likewise, parental resistance is frequently linked to educational inequalities, which reveal generational gaps in health knowledge. While most interventions focus on young people, they overlook the gatekeeping power of parents and older adults with limited information (Lubeya et al., 2023).

Although logistical problems are often blamed for issues of cost and supply (Prem et al., 2024), Kutz et al. (2023) and Asempah and Ikpebe (2024) argue that the deeper issue lies in global inequities, with vaccine distribution favouring high-income countries and structurally disadvantaging SSA. This reflects a larger flaw in global health governance, where inequitable allocation perpetuates disadvantage in the region. The constant reference to “rumoured side effects” in communities also reflects not simply misinformation, but a collective trauma shaped by past medical neglect and coercion. In such contexts, information alone cannot overcome suspicion. Instead, transformation requires visible, lived demonstrations of vaccine safety as Turiho et al. (2017) observed, seeing peers vaccinated without harm significantly shifted parental perceptions. Overcoming barriers, therefore, demands a move away from top-down information delivery and toward co-created, community-grounded approaches to health, where trust is built relationally and collectively rather than assumed.

5. Conclusion

This study explored the complex interplay between perceptions, facilitators, and barriers influencing HPV vaccine uptake across Sub-Saharan Africa. Findings reveal a sharp contrast between negative perceptions often driven by fears of infertility, bodily harm, and mistrust rooted in misinformation and positive views of the vaccine as a preventive measure against cervical cancer. While facilitators such as trusted educators, government initiatives, and public vaccination campaigns play an important role, their impact remains uneven and inconsistently applied across contexts. On the other hand, barriers extend beyond access and logistics to include deeply embedded socio-cultural, spiritual, and systemic challenges. These findings underscore that vaccine uptake in SSA is less about technical delivery and more about building trust in information, institutions, and health systems. Improving HPV vaccine coverage will therefore require more than campaigns; it calls for long-term, context-sensitive interventions that address historical mistrust and socio-cultural realities.

Recommendations

Based on these insights, practice and policy must prioritise grassroots education campaigns co-designed with local leaders, religious figures, and youth advocates to dismantle myths and translate scientific information into relatable contexts. Vaccination delivery models should also expand beyond schools to include mobile clinics and home-based outreach targeting rural and out-of-school populations. Strengthening institutional trust through permanent awareness units, empathetic frontline training, and embedding HPV vaccination in national immunisation policies with clear budget allocations is essential to reduce donor dependency. Additionally, communication strategies must be gender-inclusive and intergenerational, directly engaging parents and adolescents in patriarchal and low-literacy settings. For future research, there is a need for country-specific ethnographic studies, deeper exploration of male influencers' roles, and long-term studies on recipients' health behaviours and reproductive decisions. Furthermore, developing frameworks for co-designing vaccine strategies with communities will be vital in ensuring sustainable and equitable uptake across SSA.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest related to the preparation and publication of this manuscript. No financial, personal, academic, or institutional relationships have influenced the conduct, interpretation, or reporting of this study. All authors confirm that the research was carried out objectively and independently, with no competing interests to disclose.

References

- [1] Agimas, M.C., Adugna, D.G., Derseh, N.M., Kassaw, A., Kassie, Y.T., Abate, H.K. and Mekonnen, C.K. (2024) 'Uptake of human papilloma virus vaccine and its determinants among females in East Africa: a systematic review and meta-analysis', *BMC public health*, 24(1). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-024-18141-5>.
- [2] Ahmed, S.K., Mohammed, R.A., Nashwan, A.J., Ibrahim, R.H., Abdalla, A.Q., Ameen, B.M.M. and Khidhir, R.M. (2025) 'Using thematic analysis in qualitative research', *Journal of Medicine, Surgery, and Public Health*, 6(6), p. 100198. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.glmedi.2025.100198>.
- [3] Asempah, E. (2020) 'HPV vaccine and cervical cancer policy and policymaking research interest in sub-Saharan Africa: A scoping review', *Journal of Cancer Policy*, 26, p. 100258. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcpo.2020.100258>.
- [4] Asempah, E. and Ikpebe, E. (2024) 'Accelerating HPV vaccination in Africa for health equity', *Global Health Research and Policy*, 9(1). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41256-024-00380-z>.
- [5] Asempah, E. and Wiktorowicz, M.E. (2023) 'Understanding HPV Vaccination Policymaking in Rwanda: A Case of Health Prioritization and Public-Private-Partnership in a Low-Resource Setting', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(21), pp. 6998–6998. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20216998>.
- [6] Asubiaro, T.V. (2023) '(Under)Representation of Research Journals from Africa in Web of Science, and Scopus', *SSRN Electronic Journal [Preprint]*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4417249>.
- [7] Ayre, J. and McCaffery, K.J. (2022) 'Research Note: Thematic Analysis in Qualitative Research', *Journal of Physiotherapy*, 68(1), pp. 76–79. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jphys.2021.11.002>.
- [8] Balogun, F. and Omotade, O. (2018) "'She must have been sleeping around"...: Contextual interpretations of cervical cancer and views regarding HPV vaccination for adolescents in selected communities in Ibadan, Nigeria', *PLOS ONE*. Edited by J. Maree, 13(9), p. e0203950. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0203950>.
- [9] Balogun, F.M. and Omotade, O.O. (2022) 'Facilitators and barriers of healthcare workers' recommendation of HPV vaccine for adolescents in Nigeria: views through the lens of theoretical domains framework', *BMC Health Services Research*, 22(1). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-022-08224-7>.
- [10] Bergman, H., Buckley, B.S., Villanueva, G., Petkovic, J., Garritty, C., Lutje, V., Riveros-Balta, A.X., Low, N. and Henschke, N. (2019) 'Comparison of different human papillomavirus (HPV) vaccine types and dose schedules for prevention of HPV-related disease in females and males', *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews [Preprint]*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.cd013479>.
- [11] CASP (2024) Critical Appraisal Checklists, Critical Appraisal Skills Programme. Available at: <https://casp-uk.net/casp-tools-checklists/>.
- [12] Dzinamarira, T., Moyo, E., Dzobo, M., Mbunge, E. and Murewanhema, G. (2023) 'Cervical cancer in sub-Saharan Africa: an urgent call for improving accessibility and use of preventive services', *International Journal of Gynecologic Cancer*, 33(4). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/ijgc-2022-003957>.
- [13] Ezezika, O., Purwaha, M., Patel, H. and Mengistu, M. (2022) 'The Human Papillomavirus Vaccine Project in Rwanda: Lessons for Vaccine Implementation Effectiveness', *Global Implementation Research and Applications*, 2(4), pp. 394–403. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43477-022-00068-x>.
- [14] Hasahya, O.T., Berggren, V., Sematimba, D., Nabirye, R.C. and Kumakech, E. (2016) 'Beliefs, perceptions and health-seeking behaviours in relation to cervical cancer: a qualitative study among women in Uganda following completion of an HPV vaccination campaign', *Global Health Action*, 9(1), p. 29336. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3402/gha.v9.29336>.
- [15] Islam, J.Y., Hoyt, A.M., Ramos, S., Morgan, K., Kim, C.J., Sanjose, S. de, Butera, N., Senkomago, V., Richter, K.L., McDonald, M.A., Vielot, N.A. and Smith, J.S. (2018) 'Acceptability of two- versus three-dose human papillomavirus vaccination schedule among providers and mothers of adolescent girls: a mixed-methods study in five countries', *Cancer Causes and Control*, 29(11), pp. 1115–1130. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10552-018-1085-1>.
- [16] Jensen, J.E., Becker, G.L., Jackson, J.B. and Rysavy, M.B. (2024) 'Human Papillomavirus and Associated Cancers: A Review', *Viruses*, 16(5), p. 680. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/v16050680>.
- [17] Kamyra, C., Shearer, J., Asiimwe, G., Salisbury, N., Waiswa, P., Brinkerhoff, J. and Hozumi, D. (2016) 'Evaluating Global Health Partnerships: A Case Study of a Gavi HPV Vaccine Application Process in Uganda', *International*

Journal of Health Policy and Management, 6(6), pp. 327–338. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.15171/ijhpm.2016.137>.

- [18] Kanmodi, K.K., Egbedina, E.A., Amzat, J., Aminu, K. and Nnyanzi, L.A. (2023) ‘The state of human papillomavirus research in Africa’, *Public Health Challenges*, 2(1). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/puh2.72>.
- [19] Kisaakye, E., Namakula, J., Kihembo, C., Kisakye, A., Nsubuga, P. and Babirye, J.N. (2018) ‘Level and factors associated with uptake of Human papillomavirus infection vaccine among female adolescents in Lira District, Uganda’, *Pan African Medical Journal*, 31. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.11604/pamj.2018.31.184.14801>.
- [20] LaMontagne, D.S., Cernuschi, T., Yakubu, A., Bloem, P., Watson-Jones, D. and Kim, J.J. (2017) ‘School-Based Delivery of Vaccines to 5- to 19-Year Olds’, *Disease Control Priorities, Third Edition (Volume 8): Child and Adolescent Health and Development*, pp. 199–210. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1596/978-1-4648-0423-6_ch15.
- [21] Long, H.A., French, D.P. and Brooks, J.M. (2020) ‘Optimising the Value of the Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP) Tool for Quality Appraisal in Qualitative Evidence Synthesis’, *Research Methods in Medicine and Health Sciences*, 1(1), pp. 31–42. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/2632084320947559>.
- [22] Lubeya, M.K., Chibwasha, C.J., Mwanahamuntu, M., Mukosha, M., Frank, S.C. and Kawonga, M. (2023) “‘When you get the HPV vaccine, it will prevent cervical cancer; it will act as a shield”: adolescent girls’ knowledge and perceptions regarding the human papillomavirus vaccine in Zambia’, *Frontiers in Health Services*, 3. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3389/frhs.2023.1208458>.
- [23] Martel, C., Georges, D., Bray, F., Ferlay, J. and Clifford, G.M. (2020) ‘Global burden of cancer attributable to infections in 2018: a worldwide incidence analysis’, *The Lancet Global Health*, 8(2), pp. e180–e190. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2214-109x\(19\)30488-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2214-109x(19)30488-7).
- [24] Masika, M.M., Ogembo, J.G., Chabeda, S.V., Wamai, R.G. and Mugo, N. (2015) ‘Knowledge on HPV Vaccine and Cervical Cancer Facilitates Vaccine Acceptability among School Teachers in Kitui County, Kenya’, *PLOS ONE*. Edited by D.F. Hozbor, 10(8), p. e0135563. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0135563>.
- [25] Moosapour, H., Saeidifard, F., Aalaa, M., Soltani, A. and Larijani, B. (2021) ‘The Rationale behind Systematic Reviews in Clinical medicine: a Conceptual Framework’, *Journal of Diabetes and Metabolic Disorders*, 20(1), pp. 919–929. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40200-021-00773-8>.
- [26] Moucheraud, C., Whitehead, H.S., Songo, J., Szilagyi, P.G., Hoffman, R.M. and Kaunda-Khangamwa, B.N. (2023) ‘Malawian caregivers’ experiences with HPV vaccination for preadolescent girls: A qualitative study’, *Vaccine: X*, 14, p. 100315. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvax.2023.100315>.
- [27] Murewanhema, G., Moyo, E., Dzobo, M., Mandishora-Dube, R.S. and Dzinamarira, T. (2024) ‘Human papilloma virus vaccination in the resource-limited settings of sub-Saharan Africa: Challenges and recommendations’, *Vaccine X*, 20, pp. 100549–100549. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvax.2024.100549>.
- [28] Naeem, M., Ozuem, W., Howell, K.E. and Ranfagni, S. (2023) ‘A step-by-step Process of Thematic Analysis to Develop a Conceptual Model in Qualitative Research’, *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 22(1), pp. 1–18. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/16094069231205789>.
- [29] Odubia, J. S., Akinrinade, S., Agbeseyi, S., Sowunmi, A., Nkaroijo, D., & Ajileye, S. (2025). comparative effectiveness of ranibizumab and bevacizumab in the treatment of diabetic retinopathy: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *World Journal of Biology Pharmacy and Health Sciences*, 2025(02), 419–433. <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjbphs.2025.23.2.0790>
- [30] Paez, A. (2017) ‘Gray literature: an Important Resource in Systematic Reviews’, *Journal of Evidence-Based Medicine*, 10(3), pp. 233–240. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/jebm.12266>.
- [31] Shaheen, N., Shaheen, A., Ramadan, A., Hefnawy, M.T., Ramadan, A., Ibrahim, I., Hassanein, M., Ashour, M.E. and Flouty, O. (2023) ‘Appraising Systematic reviews: a Comprehensive Guide to Ensuring Validity and Reliability’, *Frontiers in Research Metrics and Analytics*, 8(8). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3389/frma.2023.1268045>.
- [32] Turiho, A.K., Okello, E.S., Muhwezi, W.W. and Katahoire, A.R. (2017) ‘Perceptions of human papillomavirus vaccination of adolescent schoolgirls in western Uganda and their implications for acceptability of HPV vaccination: a qualitative study’, *BMC Research Notes*, 10(1). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13104-017-2749-8>.
- [33] Venturas, C. and Umeh, K. (2017) ‘Health professional feedback on HPV vaccination roll-out in a developing country’, *Vaccine*, 35(15), pp. 1886–1891. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2017.02.052>.

- [34] Watson-Jones, D., Mugo, N., Lees, S., Mathai, M., Vusha, S., Ndirangu, G. and Ross, D.A. (2015) 'Access and Attitudes to HPV Vaccination amongst Hard-To-Reach Populations in Kenya', PLOS ONE. Edited by M.E.L. Consolaro, 10(6), p. e0123701. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0123701>.
- [35] Wilson, R.J., Leigh, L., Bah, H., Larson, H.J. and Clarke, E. (2023) 'HPV vaccination acceptance and perceptions related to fertility and population control in the Gambia: An anthropological analysis', *Vaccine*, 41(24), pp. 3647–3654. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2023.04.072>.
- [36] World Health Organisation (2020) Human papilloma virus vaccines and infertility, www.who.int. Available at: <https://www.who.int/groups/global-advisory-committee-on-vaccine-safety/topics/human-papillomavirus-vaccines/infertility>.
- [37] World Health Organisation (2024) Human papillomavirus and cancer, WHO. Available at: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/human-papilloma-virus-and-cancer>.
- [38] World Health Organisation (2025) Microsoft Power BI - HPV Vaccine Included in National Immunisation Programme, app.powerbi.com. Available at: <https://app.powerbi.com/view?r=eyJrIjoiNDIxZTFkZGUtMDQ1Ny00MDZkLThiZDktYWFIYTdkOGU2NDcwliwiLCI6ImY2MTBjMGI3LWJkMjQtNGIzOS04MTBiLTNkYzI4MGFmYjU5MCIsmMiOjh9>.
- [39] World Health Organisation Africa (2024) Accelerating action for HPV vaccination in Africa, WHO | Regional Office for Africa. Available at: <https://www.afro.who.int/news/accelerating-action-hpv-vaccination-africa>.
- [40] World Health Organization (2024) Immunization Coverage, World Health Organization. Available at: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/immunization-coverage>.

Authors short Biography

Odubia, James Success is a renowned research addict with a passion for solving public health issues through health promotion and research. His vision stems from the understanding that research is a vital tool that allows us to reflect on the past, sustain the present, and project into the future.